

Quantum Mechanics in Terms of Probability Resonances and Statistical Energy-Probability Balance

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A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas consists of particles which undergo physical collisions which are associated with the idea of causality, but we argue that reaction balance: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_3)n(e_4)$ represent steady stream energy-probability conservation and so one need not actually think in terms of direct collisions and causality i.e. one may just as well write: $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_1+e_2)$.

In the case of quantum mechanics, we argue, as we have done in previous notes, that the free particle form follows from the Lorentz invariant $A=-Et+px$. In a rest frame, there is energy, but no net momentum. We thus argue for a physical separation of the $-Et$ and px terms. We further suggest that energy is associated with a resonance in time and p momentum with one in space i.e $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. Given that $A=-Et+px$ is also the relativistic/nonrelativistic classical action, we suggest that these represent probability resonances associated with constant p motion. As a result, given that p is associated with impulse, we suggest that an interaction means forming a new resonance i.e. $p_1 \rightarrow p_2$ implies $\exp(ip_1 x) \rightarrow \exp(ip_2 x)$. As a result, interactions take place in length regions of \hbar/p . If this value is very small, as it is in the classical world, then it appears that the resonances occur at points. In the quantum world, it is the opposite.

If one wishes to treat quantum mechanics in a statistical manner, one needs to establish an energy-probability balance. Even in classical mechanics, impulses occur that change p , but now one has resonances which occur over a wavelength long piece of space. Furthermore a given p may be anywhere, so one thinks in terms of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ probabilities. We try to show that a probability-energy balance is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation. Thus we argue that quantum mechanics uses a p -probability-energy balance for the time-independent Schrodinger equation and so does not necessarily address causality and physical dynamics.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The Maxwell-Boltzmann gas involves many particles colliding with each other and the walls of a container. These collisions involve causality, but we argue that a statistical description of the problem is associated with energy-probability balance. For example, for a two body elastic collision:

$$E_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) and ((1b)) describe how energy changes while maintaining an overall equilibrium static $n(e_1)$ picture i.e. $n(e_i, \text{time}) = n(e_i)$. ((1b)) is a probability-energy balance which exists for any $e_i+e_j=E$. Thus ((1a)) and ((1b)) are equivalent to:

$$n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_1+e_2) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) shows explicitly probability energy conservation. Thus one need not think in terms of causal events, but rather in terms of probability-energy balance.

Quantum Free Particle and Special Relativity

$A = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant. In a frame in which a particle is at rest, $E = m_0c^2$ ($c=1$), but $p=0$. Thus there is a separation of energy and p . For example, a bound system has net $p=0$, but represents energy. This, we argue, is why $-Et$ and px appear as separate terms.

It may be shown that $A = -Et + px$ is the relativistic/nonrelativistic free particle action for $v=x/t$. This separation also exists in classical mechanics and in fact, the separation is necessary to have a Lorentz invariant expression. We suggest that the $-Et$ and px pieces may represent resonances or cycles described by:

$$\exp(-iEt) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(ipx) \quad ((3b))$$

These cycles follow a momentum-probability balance similar to ((2)) namely:

$$\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{and a similar expression for } \exp(-iEt).$$

If this is the case, a spatial interaction does not occur at a point, but rather a resonance is created i.e. $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x) \quad ((5))$$

where ((5)) represents a resonance which changes p to $p+k$, but $\exp(ipx)$ is probability and so this also represents probability of p - potential energy which is important for energy balance. Given that p is involved in impulses and that $V(x)$ is a function of x , one may consider free particle p resonances forming with various potential terms $\exp(ikx)$, but these represent p probability-potential energy.

A main idea, we argue, is that different resonances $\exp(ipx)$ retain their identity. Thus energy- p probability balance exists for each $\exp(ipx)$ resonance. In other words, there is a probability weight $a(p)$ associated with each $\exp(ipx)$ which adjusts in order to create this balance. Physically $\exp(ipx)$ is manifested in two-slit experiments and one may knock out particles with momentum p from single particle bound states. Thus these resonances are physical and not mathematical abstractions. To create a p -probability-energy balance at each resonance level, one has:

$$a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Summing ((6)) over p leads to the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x) W = E W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

$$((7)) \text{ may alternatively be written as: } \{-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}\} / W + V(x) = E \quad ((8))$$

We ask: Why is a normalization constant necessary in the first term on the LHS?

If one considers the free particle probability (resonance) $\exp(ipx)$, it is two-dimensional. There is a $\cos(px)$ cycle, but in the second dimension a $\sin(px)$ cycle. This ensures the modulus is 1 and we argue it represents a dynamical probability. A key feature is that $\cos(px)$ may be 0 at x_1 , but $\sin(px_1)$ is not. There is a two dimensional cycling which gives the feature of steady state motion.

In the case of a bound system, one considers $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$, so the $\sin(px)$ term drops out in the first case leaving $\cos(px)$. This represents a probability which is 0 at certain x points, but p and $p^2/2m$ are the same at all x . Thus one must be careful in the interpretation of averages of functions of p . In other words they must be normalized.

Causality

Just as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas example, one does not really need to follow the dynamics exactly, but rather focuses on $n(e)$ and e balance described through $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_1+e_2)$. Similarly in the quantum case, one considers resonances $\exp(ipx)$ which we argue form resonances with $\exp(ikx)$ terms of $V(x)$ such that there is a p -probability-energy balance. This gives rise to a $p_{rms}(x)$ i.e. $p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ which appears to be causal in x i.e. is affected by $V(x)$ at each x . In the quantum case, $\exp(ipx)$ represents probability which explains why it is repeated (wavelength) throughout space. One is interested in a probability-energy balance, not necessarily exact dynamics.

High Energy Limit

In the limit that a resonance length becomes very small with respect to the system length, $\exp(ikx)\exp(ipx)$ resonances may occur in a tiny length which is like a point in the large system. In such a case, p may be replaced with $p_{rms}(x)$ within each tiny resonance length.

Bound State Resonance

It is interesting to note that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ applies to constituent E, p 's as well as to overall ones. One may use $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ resonances without any time features to obtain an overall E_{bound} . This E_{bound} is associated with a resonance $\exp(-i E_{bound} t)$ with an $\exp(i p_{total} x)$ resonance with $p_{total}=0$. If one knocks out a particle from its bound state, it is in a momentum state of p with an $\exp(ipx)$ resonance and also an $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ resonance. The overall bound resonances or internal particle resonances are consistent with $A=-Et+px$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that based on the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$, there are two physical resonances, $\exp(-iEt)$ associated with E and time and $\exp(ipx)$ with p and x . These

resonances apply to either full systems (e.g. a bound system) or to constituents, but we note that $-Et$ and px are separated so one may treat the resonances separately. We note that A is also the relativistic/nonrelativistic classical action and suggest the resonance idea applies to the dynamics of a free particle. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, however, are considered to be probabilities.

We argue that a statistical approach to equilibrium involves energy-probability conservation. Thus one does not necessarily focus directly on the dynamics/causality of the problem, but rather on probabilities and their association with energy, momentum etc and conservation. One deals with probability balances associated with the $\exp(ipx)$ resonances for interactions with $V(x)$. Such a probability-energy balance with $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities being distinguishable yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation, but does not necessarily describe the dynamics of the system. In fact, $\exp(ipx)$ is a two-dimensional probability with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ both representing probabilities i.e. there are two x probability distributions associated with a known p . We argue that these two create the dynamics of smooth motion, but that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ is also a probabilistic picture with 1 existing at all x points. Thus one does not seem to be dealing directly with dynamics.